

INSTRUCTIONAL PRACTICES BY MULTIGRADE TEACHERS: BASIS FOR TRAINING DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This study employed a quantitative-descriptive research design to assess the instructional practices of multigrade teachers in Calisitan Elementary School, Talugtug District, Schools Division of Nueva Ecija during the school year 2023–2024. Specifically, it aimed to present the teachers' profile in terms of highest educational attainment, years of teaching experience, and relevant trainings/seminars attended; determine their teaching practices and the extent to which these were applied; and identify the problems encountered in multigrade teaching. The respondents were teachers who handled multigrade classes, and the data gathered were statistically treated using frequency, percentage, and weighted mean. Findings revealed that one teacher held a master's degree, another had earned masteral units, while the third was a bachelor's degree holder; their teaching experience ranged from three to eight years, though only one had attended a Division-level seminar. Analysis of instructional practices showed that teachers practiced classroom partition and maximization of idle time to a great extent, but relied only moderately on daily lesson logs, peer tutoring, and curriculum indigenization, while differentiated learning, cooperative learning, and collaborative parent-teacher efforts were practiced only to a slight extent, with an overall weighted mean of 3.02 or "moderate extent." In terms of challenges, the most highly serious problems were teachers' lack of readiness and absence of a training package for multigrade classes, while very serious concerns included monograde-based textbooks, lack of instructional materials, and work overload, with an overall weighted mean of 3.53 or "very serious." A training design focusing on multigrade instruction, classroom management, and monitoring and evaluation was proposed to improve teaching effectiveness.

Keywords: *Instructional Practices, Multigrade teachers, Training Design*

INTRODUCTION

The world opens the door of equity for all children to proper schooling, learning and honing the skills they need to thrive. Inclusive education covers all facets of society from children with disabilities and those who are traditionally been excluded. The United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (UNSDG) explained how important it is to reduce inequality by focusing on marginalized and disadvantaged people. The curse of poverty can break if people have access to quality education and will lead to a decrease in inequalities (United Nations Development Program as cited by De Borja, 2020).

According to De Borja (2020), the challenge of achieving quality education is perennial in the Philippine education system, especially in the equal privileges given to urban and rural children. Thus, multigrade classes were established to achieve the disparity in the opportunities given to urban and rural children.

Multigrade education is an innovative step in the educational system, especially in remote areas making school learning accessible to all. The Department of Education (DepEd) is mandated to implement multigrade education in the country as needed in the local area. Many countries in the world embrace a multigrade teaching approach as one of the interventions that resolved issues of the lack of teachers, lack of schools and few learners (Tayoni & Abocejo, 2023).

The Philippines has adopted the multigrade teaching approach as a cost-effective method of raising students' participation rates and academic achievement in rural schools (Napanan, 2021). Children tend to participate more since they are given a lot of activities together with the other grade level in a class. Teachers can design performance tasks and activities and let the learners engage in various meaningful ways to develop learners' full potential to learn. When successfully delivered, the teaching of a multigrade class is similar to that of a monograde class. It also depends on the teaching techniques of a multigrade teacher.

Sintones (2019) noted that the diversity of learners is not the problem that needs to be solved but the opportunity to deliver and accomplish better learning. The ability to manage two or more courses at once is made possible by performance-based learning in multigrade classes. Appropriate tasks and activities, aligned with the curriculum and suited to every grade level can be an impetus for knowledge and skills development. Activities done may be applicable in real-life situations when learning is collaborative in a multigrade class.

Multigrade schools have become an integral part of the Philippine education scene, making a real and significant contribution to the Education for All goals of access and equity. Multigrade teaching is an important and appropriate way to help nations reach their internationally mandated Education for All targets and national Millenium Development Goals by providing quality education. The multigrade classroom is an

organizational pattern widely used in schools. From the nineteenth century up to the present around the world, there exist multigrade schools that hold classes where one teacher is responsible for pupils belonging to different age groups, grade levels and curricula.

For many educators, multigrade instruction is not an experiment or a new educational trend, but a necessity imposed, in part, by economic and geographic conditions. In an environment dominated by graded schools, the decision to combine grades can be quite difficult, especially if constituents feel shortchanged by the decision. Nonetheless, recent proposals for school restructuring reflect renewed interest in multigrade organizations and in small-scale organizations generally.

Multigrade teaching is a term used to describe the teaching in primary education of children from several grades usually in one class. But it is capable of different definition in different countries as the following examples demonstrate. It is also not necessarily the best term to use when translated into other languages and cultures.

In the Philippines, there are areas where enrolment is low or there is lack of teachers making it necessary for different grade levels to be combined. Thus, in areas that are isolated and sparsely populated, geographically inaccessible, or deficient in educational resources, multigrade classes have been adopted as a strategy to ensure Education for All.

For multigrade schools to perform better and therefore improve learning outcomes, the curriculum should be made more relevant and responsive to the abilities of the learners. Classroom management such as appropriate grouping techniques with appropriate teacher training will enhance learning.

To fulfill the ideal of access to quality basic education for all Filipinos and to eradicate illiteracy, multigrade classes were organized as a matter of necessity for remote barangays where the number of children to be enrolled could not meet the required number to organize a single grade class and assign the necessary teacher for each class. Organization of multigrade classes is a significant provision in the law, which may improve education in the barangays and give a new deal to the rural communities. With this provision, no barangay need be without a school provided there are teachers to teach it.

In Philippine educational system, the most common classroom type is the single grade and this has been the typical classroom since the public school system is organized in the Philippines. However, in remote barangays where the number of children enrolled could not meet the required number to organize a single grade class, multigrade classes were adopted. Aside from the distance of the barangay and the small number of children for each grade level, the shortage of teachers, fund and school buildings were also among the factors that led to the organization of multigrade classes in the different parts of the country (Ballesteros, 2016).

The organization of multigrade classes is an answer to the problem on access to education for children in the remote and isolated villages in the country. Multigrade

teachers are key factors in providing meaningful learning experiences in these classes in order to sustain learners' interest and to make learning more effective.

Every child must be given an opportunity to right education in order to achieve all their aspirations in life and for sustainable development for their future. Schools in lightly populated rural areas had to resort to multigrade education to be economically workable.

Hard economic realities force people to move to bigger towns and cities. The constant demand for better schools, effective principals, qualified teachers and an improved service to the communities coupled with the demand for better working conditions and salaries for teachers could have drained the education budget even further. To keep in line with the four major policies of education namely equity, access, quality and democracy, the operation of smaller, rural multigrade schools has become a necessity.

Multigrade education involves the teaching of children from two or more grade levels in one classroom. Such contexts need the employment of teaching methodologies and classroom organization and supervision. Seeing as multigrade classes are lesser and can be recognized more inexpensively than normal schools in big cities, multigrade schools are located closer to where the children live.

Multigrade teaching is a situation in which one teacher has to teach many grades all at the same time. Some multigrade teachers may teach two grades, but some teach three or four grades. In the traditional single-grade teaching, the teacher teaches only one grade. The learners in each grade are usually of the same age but may differ in abilities. The multigrade classroom mixes children with different skills and aptitudes, different developmental levels and needs while working together under the guidance of one teacher.

The main function of the multigrade teacher is to teach learners by imparting knowledge. The teacher must be able to develop skills and inculcate desirable values and attitudes among learners. He is expected to be versatile and to utilize different strategies to make learning meaningful and effective for all learners in his or her classroom, no matter what individual differences may exist among the learners.

Realizing the implications of all these things, the researcher conducted a study to assess the instructional practices of multigrade teachers in Calisitan Elementary School, Talugtog District, Schools Division of Nueva Ecija during the school year 2023-2024.

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on Piaget's Cognitive Development Theory as cited by Cherry (2019). Jean Piaget's theory of cognitive development suggests that children move through four different stages of mental development. His theory focuses not only on understanding how children acquire knowledge, but also on understanding the nature of intelligence.

Piaget's stages are: sensorimotor stage (birth to 2 years), preoperational stage (ages 2 to 7), concrete operational stage (ages 7 to 11), and formal operational stage (ages 12 and up). Piaget believed that children take an active role in the learning process, acting much like scientists as they perform experiments, make observations, and learn about the world. As kids interact with the world around them, they continually add new knowledge, build upon existing knowledge, and adapt previously held ideas to accommodate new information.

Much of Piaget's interest in the cognitive development of children was inspired by his observations of his own nephew and daughter. These observations reinforced his budding hypothesis that children's minds were not merely smaller versions of adult minds. Children were largely treated simply as smaller versions of adults. Piaget was one of the first to identify that the way that children think is different from the way adults think. Instead, he proposed, intelligence is something that grows and develops through a series of stages. Older children do not just think more quickly than younger children, he suggested. Instead, there are both qualitative and quantitative differences between the thinking of young children versus older children. In Piaget's view, early cognitive development involves processes based upon actions and later progresses to changes in mental operations.

In the sensorimotor stage (birth to 2 years), the infant knows the world through their movements and sensations. Children learn about the world through basic actions such as sucking, grasping, looking, and listening. Infants learn that things continue to exist even though cannot be seen (object permanence). They are separate beings from the people and objects around them. They realize that their actions can cause things to happen in the world around them.

During this earliest stage of cognitive development, infants and toddlers acquire knowledge through sensory experiences and manipulating objects. A child's entire experience at the earliest period of this stage occurs through basic reflexes, senses and motor responses. It is during the sensorimotor stage that children go through a period of dramatic growth and learning. As kids interact with their environment, they are continually making new discoveries about how the world works.

The cognitive development that occurs during this period takes place over a relatively short period of time and involves a great deal of growth. Children not only learn how to perform physical actions such as crawling and walking; they also learn a great deal about language from the people with whom they interact. Piaget also broke this stage down into a number of different substances. It is during the final part of the sensorimotor stage that early representational thought emerges. By learning that objects are separate and distinct entities and they have an existence of their own outside of individual perception, children are then able to begin to attach names and words to objects.

In the preoperational stage (ages 2 to 7 years), children begin to think symbolically and learn to use words and pictures to represent objects. Children at this stage tend to be egocentric and struggle to see things from the perspective of others. While they are

getting better with language and thinking, they still tend to think about things in very concrete terms. The foundations of language development may have been laid during the previous stage, but it is the emergence of language that is one of the major hallmarks of the preoperational stage of development. Children become much more skilled at pretend play during this stage of development, yet continue to think very concretely about the world around them. At this stage, kids learn through pretend play but still struggle with logic and taking the point of view of other people. They also often struggle with understanding the idea of constancy.

During the concrete operational stage (ages 7 to 11 years), children begin to think logically about concrete events. They begin to understand the concept of conservation and their thinking becomes more logical and organized, but still very concrete. Children begin using inductive logic, or reasoning from specific information to a general principle.

While children are still very concrete and literal in their thinking at this point in development, they become much more adept at using logic. The egocentrism of the previous stage begins to disappear as kids become better at thinking about how other people might view a situation. While thinking becomes much more logical during the concrete operational stage, it can also be very rigid. Kids at this point in development tend to struggle with abstract and hypothetical concepts.

During this stage, children also become less egocentric and begin to think about how other people might think and feel. Kids in the concrete operational stage also begin to understand that their thoughts are unique to them and that not everyone else necessarily shares their thoughts, feelings and opinions.

At the formal operational stage (ages 12 and up), the adolescent or young adult begins to think abstractly and reason about hypothetical problems. Abstract thought emerges and teens begin to think more about moral, philosophical, ethical, social, and political issues that require theoretical and abstract reasoning. They begin to use deductive logic, or reasoning from a general principle to specific information.

The final stage of Piaget's theory involves an increase in logic, the ability to use deductive reasoning, and an understanding of abstract ideas. At this point, people become capable of seeing multiple potential solutions to problems and think more scientifically about the world around them. The ability to think about abstract ideas and situations is the key hallmark of the formal operational stage of cognitive development. The ability to systematically plan for the future and reason about hypothetical situations are also critical abilities that emerge during this stage.

It is important to note that Piaget did not view children's intellectual development as a quantitative process; that is, kids do not just add more information and knowledge to their existing knowledge as they get older. Instead, Piaget suggested that there is a qualitative change in how children think as they gradually process through these four

stages. A child at age 7 does not just have more information about the world than he did at age 2; there is a fundamental change in how he thinks about the world.

To better understand some of the things that happen during cognitive development, it is important first to examine a few of the important ideas and concepts introduced by Piaget and some of the factors that influence how children learn and grow.

A schema describes both the mental and physical actions involved in understanding and knowing. Schemas are categories of knowledge that help to interpret and understand the world. In Piaget's view, a schema includes both a category of knowledge and the process of obtaining that knowledge. As experiences happen, this new information is used to modify, add to, or change previously existing schemas.

Assimilation is the process of taking in new information into already existing schemas. The process is somewhat subjective because people tend to modify experiences and information slightly to fit in with the preexisting beliefs.

Another part of adaptation involves changing or altering the existing schemas in light of new information is a process known as accommodation. Accommodation involves modifying existing schemas, or ideas, as a result of new information or new experiences. New schemas may also be developed during this process.

Piaget believed that all children try to strike a balance between assimilation and accommodation, which is achieved through a mechanism Piaget called equilibration. As children progress through the stages of cognitive development, it is important to maintain a balance between applying previous knowledge (assimilation) and changing behavior to account for new knowledge (accommodation). Equilibration helps explain how children can move from one stage of thought to the next.

Conceptual Framework

The 1987 Philippine Constitution guarantees the right to education of every Filipino. It provides that "The State shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make education accessible to all." The right of every Filipino to quality basic education is further emphasized in Republic Act 9155 or the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2011. This law reaffirms the policy of the State to protect and promote the rights of all Filipinos by providing free and compulsory basic education with the skills, knowledge and the values they need to become caring, self-reliant, productive and patriotic citizens.

With the implementation of Republic Act 10533 known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, the State likewise affirmed its commitment that every graduate of basic education shall be empowered individual who has learned, through a program that is rooted on sound educational principles and geared towards excellence, the foundation for learning throughout life, the competence to engage in work and be productive, the ability to coexist in fruitful harmony with local and global communities, the capability to

engage in autonomous, creative, and critical thinking, and the capacity and willingness to transform others and oneself.

The Multigrade Program in Philippine Education (MPPE) was launched in 1993 through DepEd Order 83 and subsequently in 1997, the Department issued order No.96 to support the implementation of the MPPE. The policy declares building of schools in the school-less barangays where enrolment and population growth trends warrants the establishment of new schools and to organize multigrade classes to offer complete elementary education.

Since the implementation of the MPPE, the Bureau of Learning Delivery (BLD) developed various instructional materials, trained teachers and administrators, improved the learning environment, increased school participation, and importantly, enhanced the holding power or pupil retention in school.

Multigrade education is one of the measures instituted to realize the global commitment of 164 United Nations members to make education available and accessible to all (UNESCO, 2021). This school system is combining two or three grade levels in one class because the enrollees are few and is often carried out in remote villages. This school system is intended for children in far flung areas. Teachers go to the remote communities to ensure that education is accessible to all children.

Multigrade teaching offers advantages aside from its main purpose of making education accessible to the remote villages. Some of the benefits are opportunities for re-teaching becomes real since teachers handle small number of pupils compared to regular schools; academic, physical and social competition between peers is reduced since cooperation is more emphasized rather than competition; older students have the opportunity to teach younger ones so they become more responsible; longer time spent by the same teachers with students increases more trust, understanding and positive relationships; and teachers could spend more time with the children after classes (Word Press, 2020).

Several studies on multigrade teaching were also conducted in the Philippines. Brecio (2023) showed that handling multigrade classes was hardly manageable. Classrooms were sub-standard; school furniture and textbooks were described not enough while school equipment and instructional tools and devices were none at all. Pupils form multigrade classes excelled in Mathematics and performed fairly in other subjects. Fifty percent of the teachers had no seminar in multigrade teaching. The administrative support on instruction development and instructional materials development were only satisfactory.

Ocampo (2016) documented best practices of multigrade teaching in Luna, Apayao. Results revealed that the multigrade teachers of Luna are relatively young and they are in their prime years of teaching. All of the teachers handled two grade levels. Most of them live quite a distance for five to twenty five kilometers away from school. There are sixteen practices of the multigrade teachers applied in Luna. These are the use

of Daily Lesson Log (DLL), “To Do List”, Shifting Lessons, use of Para teacher of the little teachers, cooperative learning and peer tutoring, multiple intelligence class, instructional materials (IMs) resource sharing, organizing instructional materials, indigenizing the curriculum, attending INSETs, collaborative effort between parents and teachers in promoting projects, partition of class, the use of anecdotal record, treatment of the minority pupils and maximization of idle time.

The Department of Education’s Vision, Mission and Values (VMV) statements serve as guiding principles in its unwavering thrust to provide quality education that cultivates passion for the country that is anchored on a set of core values.

The Department of Education (DepEd) vision dreams of Filipinos who passionately love their country and whose values and competencies enable them to realize their full potential and contribute meaningfully to building the nation. As a learner-centered public institution, DepEd continuously improves itself to better serve its stakeholders.

The DepEd mission is to protect and promote the right of every Filipino to quality, equitable, culture-based, and complete basic education where students learn in a child-friendly, gender-sensitive, safe, and motivating environment; teachers facilitate learning and constantly nurture every learner; administrators and staff, as stewards of the institution, ensure an enabling and supportive environment for effective learning to happen; family, community, and other stakeholders are actively engaged and share responsibility for developing life-long learners.

Figure 1 presents the schematic diagram of the conceptual framework of the study through the Input-Process-Output Model.

Inputs of the study include the following; (1) profile of the multigrade teachers in terms of highest educational attainment, number of years teaching experience and relevant trainings/seminars attended; (2) instructional practices of the multigrade teachers and extent of practice; and (3) problems met by the teachers in teaching multigrade classes and how serious are they.

Based on the findings, a training design was proposed to improve multigrade teaching in Calisitan Elementary School, Talugtug District, Schools Division of Nueva Ecija.

Figure 1
Schematic Diagram of the Conceptual Framework of the Study

Research Questions

This study assessed the instructional practices of the multigrade teachers in Calisitan Elementary School, Talugtug District, Schools Division of Nueva Ecija during the school year 2023-2024.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the profile of the multigrade teachers in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 Highest educational attainment;
 - 1.2 Number of years of teaching multigrade classes; and
 - 1.3 Relevant trainings/seminars attended?
2. What are the practices of the multigrade teachers and to what extent are they being practiced?
3. What are the problems met by the teachers in teaching multigrade classes and how serious are they?
4. What training design can be proposed to improve the teaching of multigrade classes?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter deals with the methods and procedures utilized in the study. It includes the research design, the sources of data, instrumentation and data collection, and the tools for data analysis.

This study employed the quantitative-descriptive research design in the assessment of the instructional practices of the multigrade teachers in Calisitan Elementary School, Talugtug District, Schools Division of Nueva Ecija during the school year 2023-2024.

The quantitative-descriptive research design was used to present the profile of the multigrade teachers in terms of highest educational attainment, number of years teaching experience, and relevant trainings/seminars attended. It was also used to focus on the practices of the multigrade teachers and to what extent are they being practiced. Further, it was utilized to look into the problems met by the multigrade teachers and how serious are they.

Based on the findings of the study, a training design was proposed to improve the teaching of multigrade classes.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study was conducted in Calisitan Elementary School, Talugtug District, Schools Division of Nueva Ecija during the school year 2023-2024. It was delimited to the assessment of the instructional practices of the multigrade teachers in teaching multigrade classes.

The specific concerns of the study include the profile of the multigrade teachers in terms of highest educational attainment, number of years teaching experience, and relevant trainings/seminars attended. The study is also concerned with the practices of the multigrade teachers and to what extent are they being practiced. Furthermore, it also looked into the problems met by the multigrade teachers and how serious are they.

Based on the findings, a training design was proposed to improve the teaching of multigrade classes.

Significance of the Study

The education system must provide a strong base to contribute to the economic and social development of the country.

This study, therefore, will be of great importance to the following:

DepEd Policy Makers

The assessment results can be used as basis for determining future programs in the teaching of different learning areas, particularly in multigrade classes.

School Administrators

The results of the study can be used as a frame of reference for planning future activities/exercises in the teaching of a multigrade class.

Multigrade Teachers

The results of the study can motivate them to prepare instructional materials that are relevant and suited to the needs of their multigrade learners.

Multigrade Learners

They are the direct beneficiaries of the results of the study, thus, their weaknesses can be addressed for a better academic performance.

Researcher Himself

The research process itself which enable the researcher to come up with intervention strategies will make him a competent teacher in terms of creativity and innovativeness which characterize productive, efficient and effective teachers.

Future Researchers

They can conduct similar studies on a wider scope where the present study can serve as model or prototype.

Definition of Terms

For a better understanding of the study, the following terms are hereby operationally defined:

Multigrade Class

Conceptually, it is defined as a class of two or more grades under the responsibility of one teacher in a complete or incomplete elementary school. The term multigrade is used to include a combination class composed of two grades or multigrade class composed of three or more grades. As used in the study, this refers to the combined classes in Calisitan Elementary School, Talugtug District, Schools Division of Nueva Ecija.

Multigrade Teaching

This refers to the teaching of learners in a class of several grade levels with different curricula under the supervision of one teacher.

Practices

Conceptually, these are techniques teachers use to help students become independent, strategic learners. These strategies become learning strategies when students independently select the appropriate ones and use them effectively to accomplish tasks or meet goals (Napanan, 2021). In this study, practices were measured and described as follows: 5 – Full Extent; 4 – Great Extent; 3 – Moderate Extent; 2 – Slight Extent; and 1 – Not At All.

Profile

As used in the study, this refers to characteristics of the multigrade teachers in terms of highest educational attainment, number of years teaching experience, and relevant trainings/seminars attended.

Proposed Training Design

This refers to the output of the study. It means developing new training and educational lessons for the multigrade teachers. It roots out the gaps in training and fills them in with new materials for better performance. It also allows teachers to grow their skills rather than become static in their roles.

Sources of Data

This study was conducted in Calisitan Elementary School, Talugtug District in the Province of Nueva Ecija during the school year 2023-2024 where the respondents were the teachers handling multigrade classes.

Instrumentation and Data Collection

The main instrument used in gathering data for the study was a constructed questionnaire which consists of three parts. Part I focused on the profile of the multigrade teachers in terms of highest educational attainment, number of years of teaching experience and relevant trainings and seminars attended; Part II determined the practices of the multigrade teachers and the extent of practice of such; and Part III looked into the problems met by the multigrade teachers and how serious are they. Upon completion of the questionnaire, it was presented to the researcher's adviser. Suggestions were incorporated to improve the instrument.

The researcher personally administered the distribution of the questionnaires to ensure 100% retrieval. Data gathered were tabulated and interpreted using appropriate statistical tools.

Tools for Data Analysis

The following tools were employed to treat the data statistically:

1. Frequency and Percentage

These were used to answer sub-problem number 1.

The formula is:

$$P = \frac{f}{N}$$

Where:

P = Percentage

f = frequency

N = Number of respondents

2. Weighted Mean

This was utilized to answer sub-problem numbers 2 and 3.

The formula is:

$$WM = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$$

Where:

WM = Weighted Mean

$\sum fx$ = the sum of the products per column

N = the number of respondents

Data gathered were interpreted by using the following references:

Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)	
		For Sub-Problem No. 2	For Sub-Problem No.3
5	4.50 – 5.00	Full Extent (FE)	Highly Serious (HS)
4	3.50 – 4.49	Great Extent (FE)	Very Serious (VS)
3	2.50 – 3.49	Moderate Extent (ME)	Moderately Serious (MS)
2	1.50 – 2.49	Slight Extent (SE)	Slightly Serious (SS)
1	1.00 – 1.49	Not At All (NAA)	Not a Problem (NP)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Multigrade Teachers in Terms of Variables

This section presents the profile of the multigrade teachers in Calisitan Elementary School, Talugtug District, Schools Division of Nueva Ecija during the school year 2023 – 2024 in terms of highest educational attainment, number of years of teaching multigrade classes and relevant trainings/ seminars attended to answer sub-problem number 1. The data are presented in Tables 1A, 1B and 1C.

Highest Educational Attainment

Educational attainment of teachers is an important determinant of course outcomes to keep pace with the demands of global competitiveness. Table 1A presents the profile of the multigrade teachers in terms of highest educational attainment.

Table 1A
Profile of Multigrade Teachers in Terms of
Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	<i>f</i>	%
Master's degree	1	33.34
Earned masteral units	1	33.33
Bachelor's degree	1	33.33
TOTAL	3	100%

In terms of highest educational attainment, Table 1A showed that one teacher is a holder of master's degree, another earned masteral units and the remaining is a graduate of bachelor's degree.

These results indicate that the multigrade teachers are aware of the importance of graduate studies. They have the desire to advance in their career for professional growth and to make them more effective in their teaching. Considering that they are in pursuit of advance studies in the graduate education program, it is implied that they are determined to grow professionally and aspire for greater heights in their professional life.

Number of Years of Teaching Multigrade Classes

Teaching experience matters with each year in the profession, hopefully leading to better learner performance. The profile of the multigrade teachers in terms of number of years of teaching multigrade classes is presented in Table 1B.

Table 1B
Profile of Multigrade Teachers in Terms of
Number of Years of Teaching Multigrade Classes

Number of Years	<i>f</i>	%
7 – 9 years	1	33.34
4 – 6 years	1	33.33
1 – 3 years	1	33.33
TOTAL	3	100%

As presented in Table 1B, in terms of number of years of teaching multigrade classes, one teacher has been teaching multigrade classes for eight years; one for six years; and the other one for 3 years.

In the study, the findings suggest that beginning teachers are doing as well or better than teachers with more years of experience, but that the overall quality of teaching could be higher. As such, better support and professional learning is necessary to improve the quality of teaching for all teachers, not just those at the beginning of their career. These results imply that the number of years of experience in teaching does not matter as long as teachers can impart knowledge to the learners and achieve their goals in teaching.

Relevant Trainings/ Seminars Attended

Teacher training is important in the teaching process and usually needed for the educational system to run effectively. Table 1C presents the profile of the multigrade teachers in terms of relevant trainings/ seminars attended.

Table 1C
Profile of Multigrade Teachers in Terms of
Relevant Trainings/ Seminars Attended

Number of Trainings/ Seminars	<i>f</i>	%
Division level seminar	1	33.33
No seminar	2	66.67
TOTAL	3	100%

As presented in Table 1C, only one have attended a seminar on the division level; the other teachers have not attended any seminar.

Multigrade schools deliver an alternative form of formal education. As an alternative modality of education, multigrade requires strategies and techniques different from the conventional classroom setting. Thus, it is necessary for teachers to learn other effective ways of delivering education. This demands that multigrade competencies be improved and their knowledge and skills be constantly upgraded through trainings.

Practices of the Multigrade Teachers and Extent of Practice

This section presents the practices of the multigrade teachers and the extent of practice of such to answer sub-problem number 2. The data are presented in Table 2.

Table 2
Practices of Multigrade Teachers

PRACTICES	WM	DE
Use Daily Lesson Log	3.33	ME
Come up with a to-do-list	3.67	GE
Shift lessons	2.67	ME
Use Para teachers like parents or more mature classmates	3.67	GE
Conduct peer tutoring	3.33	ME
Use differentiated learning activities	2.33	SE
Use cooperative learning	2.33	SE
Consider multiple intelligences	2.33	SE
Share instructional materials	3.33	ME
Develop instructional materials	2.67	ME
Indigenize the curriculum/ use of Mother Tongue	2.67	ME
Conduct in-service trainings	2.33	SE
Promote collaborative effort between parents and teachers in projects	2.33	SE
Observe partition of class	4.33	GE
Prepare anecdotal records	2.33	SE
Conduct positive treatment of minority	3.33	ME
Maximize idle time	4.33	GE
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.02	ME
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Full Extent (FE)
4	3.50-4.49	Great Extent (GE)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderate Extent (ME)
2	1.50-2.49	Slight Extent (SE)
1	1.00-1.49	Not At All (NAA)

As presented in Table 2, practices of the multigrade teachers in Calisitan Elementary School which were practiced to a “great extent” were coming up with a to do list, use of para teachers like parents or more mature classmates, observation of partition of class, and maximization of idle time.

The “to do list” with weighted mean of 3.67, is a listing of daily activities listed in chronological order in the order of priority or importance. One of the most reasons for keeping a to-do-list is the organization. Organizing tasks with a list can make everything

much more manageable. Having a list of all tasks will allow teachers to make plans. According to Ocampo (2016), fifteen minutes spent planning could save an hour of execution time. Handling double grade means double work and no planning is waste of time.

Use of para teachers were practiced to a great extent with weighted mean of 3.67. The teacher entrusts the lesson to the learner who understands the lesson well. This is very effective in lessons to develop skills such as reading, counting arithmetic and others. The teacher then allows the others to be taught by the said learner. Learners learn how to help one another and themselves. At an early age, learners are expected to develop independence. The effective multigrade teacher establishes a climate to promote and develop this independence.

Partition of classes with weighted mean of 4.33 is a good practice applied by several schools to divide or to out a partition during discussion. This is to avoid disturbance on both grade levels that leads them to concentrate on their own works.

Maximization of idle time, with weighted mean of 4.33 was practiced to a “great extent.” Idle time is unproductive time and is associated with waiting. This should not be observed in classes. Maximizing learners’ time can contribute to orderliness in class. To keep learners busy during in-between or vacant time, they are given opportunity to do some projects. Learners in higher grade levels are encouraged to play chess, sci-damath, word factory and scrabble to improve their vocabulary and social skills. Maximization of idle time is also important in maintaining good mental and physical health. Learners learn by themselves through independent learning forming an interactive learning community.

Practices applied to a “moderate extent” were the use of Daily Lesson Log (WM=3.33), shifting of lessons (WM=2.67), conduct of peer tutoring (WM=3.33), instructional material sharing (WM=3.33), developing instructional materials (WM=2.67), indigenizing the curriculum / use of Mother Tongue (WM=2.67), and conduct of positive treatment of minority (WM=3.33).

For time management, Daily Lesson Log is used as the guidepost sketch of everyday activities. In shifting lessons as an evaluation of instruction, the teacher leaves an activity to the other grade while the other class is ongoing. In peer tutoring, as classroom instructional preparation and management, the higher performing learner is paired with a lower performing learner to review critical academic or behavioral concepts.

For preparation and utilization of instructional materials, sharing of instructional materials enables other teachers to collect ideas in improving and even inventing instructional materials to be used by their colleagues, organizing instructional material for daily lessons and explanation of lessons by the use of vernacular if the learners cannot comprehend. And lastly, in homeroom guidance is treatment of minority to boost their self-confidence.

These results imply that the multigrade teachers practice various techniques and strategies so they can impart knowledge to the learners not just to follow a curriculum. A

combined class of learners differs from the conventional type of a class of a single grade. That means that the way the learners of the multigrade class should be taught must be different as well. The function of the teacher in the multigrade classroom is multidimensional or much more complicated and demanding than the role of the teacher in the monograde school. Thus, the multigrade teacher is expected to utilize different strategies to make learning meaningful and effective.

Problems Met by the Teachers in Teaching Multigrade Classes

This section presents the problems met by the teachers in teaching multigrade classes to answer sub-problem number 3. The data are presented in Table 3.

Table 3
Problems Met in the Teaching of Multigrade Classes

PROBLEMS	WM	DE
Teachers not ready to handle multigrade classes	4.67	HS
Textbooks almost entirely on a monograde content	4.33	VS
No training package for multigrade teachers	4.67	HS
Inconsistencies in teaching methodologies	3.33	MS
Lack of instructional materials	3.67	VS
Need for effective supervision	2.67	MS
Classroom management	2.67	MS
No standard activity for entire class	3.33	MS
Inadequate school facilities	2.67	MS
Lack of incentives for teachers in multiple classes	3.33	MS
Work overload	4.33	VS
Lack of support from school administrators	2.67	MS
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.53	VS
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Serious (HS)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Serious (VS)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Serious (MS)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Serious (SS)
1	1.00-1.49	Not a Problem (NP)

As gleaned in Table 3, problems met by the teachers in teaching multigrade classes are “highly serious”, “very serious” and “moderately serious.” “Highly serious” problems include teachers not ready to handle multigrade classes and no training package for multigrade teachers with weighted means of 4.67 for both indicators. Most new teachers are often assigned to handle multigrade classes, a situation they did not experience during their teacher training days. They are teaching in classes without relevant knowledge and skills to teach in these classes. This problem is compounded by lack of training on their part. Most teachers were not trained in multigrade teaching since

teacher training programs did not focus on practical issues and techniques for handling multigrade classes. They attended workshops for only a couple of days and those intended for simple grade classes. These imply that these teachers have to adapt their general knowledge of teaching to their multigrade classrooms on their own.

The “very serious” problems are the following: textbooks almost entirely on a monograde context, lack of instructional materials and work overload with weighted mean of 4.33, 3.67 and 4.33, respectively. There are textbooks / workbooks for all grades in the classroom and teachers use them for the grades that they are prescribed for. However, there are no instructional materials written for multigrade classes. The teachers alluded to the fact that there is too much work for teachers in multigrade classrooms. They assert that there is too much planning in multigrade classes and that they also have to prepare two assessment tasks per subject and this is a lot of work. They argue that, although they gave few learners in their classrooms, the number of subjects they teach is too much because they teach subjects as normal class.

“Moderately serious” problems include inconsistencies in teaching methodologies, need for effective supervision, classroom management, no standard activity for entire class, inadequate school facilities, lack of incentives for teachers in multiple classes, and lack of support from school administrators with weighted means that ranged from 2.67 to 3.33.

For many educators, multigrade instruction is not an experiment or a new educational trend, but a necessity imposed, in part, by economic and geographic conditions. In an environment dominated by graded schools, the decision to combine grades can be quite difficult, thus, these problems arise.

Although these challenges happen in the day-to-day life of multigrade teachers, some coping mechanisms were developed for them to carry on their duties and responsibilities of delivering quality education to their learners. Naparan (2021) documented these coping mechanisms such as strengthening one’s faith through prayers, utilizing the power of the Internet and its vast information readily available at the end of their fingertips, following a timetable in doing duties and responsibilities, and finally, renewing one’s mind in the process of self-conditioning.

With these mechanisms came the results of sharing resources among the multigrade teachers, developing flexible grouping practices to meet the needs of their learners, conducting cooperative-collaborative learning, connecting lessons to real life, and integrating technology.

Proposed Training Design for Multigrade Teachers

This section presents the proposed training design for multigrade teachers to improve the teaching of multigrade classes to answer sub-problem number 4.

The training design proposed three sessions, namely Introduction to Multigrade Instruction, Classroom Management Techniques and Strategies for Teaching and Learning and Monitoring and Evaluation.

Conclusions

This study employed the quantitative-descriptive research design in the assessment of the instructional practices of the multigrade teachers in Calisitan Elementary School, Talugtug District, Schools Division of Nueva Ecija during the school year 2023-2024.

The quantitative-descriptive research design was used to present the profile of the multigrade teachers in terms of highest educational attainment, number of years teaching experience, and relevant trainings/seminars attended. It was also used to focus on the practices of the multigrade teachers and to what extent are they being practiced. Further, it was utilized to look into the problems met by the multigrade teachers and how serious are they.

Based on the findings of the study, a training design was proposed to improve the teaching of multigrade classes.

This study was conducted in Calisitan Elementary School, Talugtug District, Schools Division of Nueva Ecija during the school year 2023-2024 where the respondents were the teachers handling multigrade classes.

Frequency and percentage and weighted mean were utilized in the study to treat the data statistically.

Summary of Findings

Profile of the Multigrade Teachers in Terms of Variables

In terms of highest educational attainment, one multigrade teacher holds a master's degree; another had earned masteral units and the other one is a graduate of bachelor's degree.

In terms of number of years of teaching multigrade classes, one teacher has been teaching multigrade classes for eight years; another has been a multigrade teacher for six years; and the other one for three years.

In terms of relevant trainings/ seminars attended, one multigrade teacher attended seminar on the Division level while two teachers have not attended any relevant seminar.

Practices of the Multigrade Teachers

Multigrade teachers practice the following to a great extent: Come up with a To Do List (WM=3.67), use of para teachers (WM=3.67), observation of partition of class (WM=4.33), and maximization of idle time (WM=4.33). Multigrade teachers practice the following to a moderate extent: Use of Daily Lesson Log (WM=3.33), shifting lessons

(WM=2.67), conduct of peer tutoring (WM=3.33), development of instructional materials (WM=2.67), indigenization of the curriculum / use of mother tongue (WM=2.67), and conduct of positive treatment of minority (WM=3.33).

Multigrade teachers practice the following to a slight extent: use of differentiated learning activities (WM=2.33), use of cooperative learning (WM=2.33), considering multiple intelligences (WM=2.33), conduct of in-service trainings (WM=2.33), promotion of collaborative effort between parents and teachers in promoting projects (WM=2.33), and preparation of anecdotal record (WM=2.33).

The overall weighted mean was 3.02 for descriptive equivalent of “moderate extent.”

Problems Met By the Teachers in Teaching Multigrade Classes

“Highly serious” problems met by the teachers in teaching multigrade classes were: teachers not ready to handle multigrade classes (WM=4.67) and no training package for multigrade teachers (WM=4.67).

“Very serious” problems were: textbooks almost entirely on a monograde content (WM=4.33), lack of instructional materials (WM=3.67), and work overload (WM=4.33).

“Moderately serious” problems were: inconsistencies in teaching methodologies (WM=3.33), need for effective supervision (WM=2.67), classroom management (WM=2.67), no standard activity for entire class (WM=3.33), inadequate school facilities (WM=2.67), lack of incentives for teachers in multigrade classes (WM=3.33), and lack of support from school administrators (WM=2.67).

The overall weighted mean was 3.53 for descriptive equivalent of “very serious” problems.

Proposed Training Design

A training design was proposed to improve the teaching of multigrade classes which focused on three sessions, namely Introduction to Multigrade Instruction, Classroom Management Techniques and Strategies for Teaching and Learning and Monitoring and Evaluation.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The multigrade teachers are enrolled in post-graduate program, have been teaching for three to eight years and have attended seminars on the Division level.

Generally, the teachers practice multigrade teaching to a moderate extent which indicates within reasonable limits.

Problems met by the multigrade teachers include their being not ready to handle multigrade classes and the absence of training package for them.

The proposed training design focused on Introduction to Multigrade Instruction, Classroom Management Techniques and Strategies for Teaching and Learning and Monitoring and Evaluation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations were offered:

The proposed training design should be promoted to school authorities concerned for possible implementation to improve the teaching in multigrade classes.

An appropriate and effective mechanism for regular supervision, monitoring and evaluation should be developed for the teachers handling multigrade classes.

School administrators should schedule regular visits to the multigrade schools to guide teachers on administrative concerns.

The multigrade teachers should develop instructional plans before school opening including their teaching needs and submit these to the principal for provision of support. Other researchers may conduct a similar study on a wider scope to validate the findings of the study.

Proposed Training Design for Multigrade Teachers

Rationale

Multigrade teaching is among the programs identified as a means to implement and address the problem of access, given the lack of teachers, schools and materials. However, this has brought about a concern for the quality of education. Thus, this training design is proposed for providing multigrade classes while ensuring a high quality of education.

General Objectives

To enhance the capabilities of teachers in planning and implementing instruction in multigrade classes as well as in evaluating learner performance.

Specific Objectives

Teacher trainees are expected to:

Acquire deeper understanding of the philosophy, goals, objectives, special features of multigrade teaching and the different roles of teachers in multigrade teaching.

Demonstrate competence in:

- The preparation of lesson plans, tests and instructional materials
- The use of instructional materials
- The use of different teaching strategies
- Drawing in a community support
- Structuring classrooms for effective multigrade teaching

Resources Required

- Build capacity of project managers: study tours, regional workshops
- Expand capability of institutions
- Equipment/ other facilities
- Production of materials
- Financial support for training and materials and curriculum development
- Expert assistance
- Development and production of materials
- Training
- Management of project
- Curriculum and instruction
- Information on multigrade teaching
- Brochures
- Literature

Guidelines

- The workshop introduction
- The ice-breaker activity for this workshop should be for 10 minutes.

- Group planning
- Divide the workshop participants into large groups and then subdivide each of these into smaller groups. Be sure that these are equal number of groups.

Session 1

Introduction to Multigrade Instruction

Objectives:

At the end of the session, participants should be able to:
List the challenges of multigrade classroom teaching as well as the advantages of multigrade instruction for learners and teachers
Evaluate and determine their strengths and needs improvement in regards to multigrade teaching practice
Identify the priorities for training workshops

Materials:

Flipchart paper and markers
Index cards
Training schedule

Duration: 3 hours

Training Steps

Step 1

Challenges (workshop – 30 mins)
Instructions:

Ask everyone to reflect on three challenges that they might encounter as a teacher in a multigrade classroom.

Ask them to write 2 or 3 of these challenges on index cards.

Divide participants into small groups.

In the large group, participants place their index cards on the talk.

Each group takes a few minutes to read the index cards of its different members.

Step 2

Five Fundamental Elements of Multigrade Classrooms (15 mins)
Instructions:

Use flipchart sheets to present the principal elements of a multigrade classroom. The facilitator presents the five themes and provides an explanation for each category along with its importance to multigrade instruction.

Themes:

1. Identification of learning resources
2. Techniques for classroom management
3. Multigrade planning tools
4. Managing the class

5. Monitoring and evaluation of learning

Step 3

Categorizing Challenges By Theme (15 mins)

Instructions:

Each group decides on where to place their index cards among the five categories. Place the index cards on the flipchart paper with the appropriate theme. Everyone looks at all the index cards put up by other participants.

Step 4

Similarities Between Monograde and Multigrade (30 mins)

Instructions:

Ask the group to reflect on the numerous differences and the great diversity that exists between the learners in their classes.

Ask half of the group to write a list with all the types of diversity that exists among learners in a monograde classroom. Ask the other groups to think about and write a list of differences between learners in a multigrade classroom.

Age, ability, developmental level, past history, experience, motivation, interests are all examples of diversity among learners. Trainers should walk among the groups to be certain that they have understood the activity's objective.

After 10 to 15 minutes, ask group to share their lists. Begin with lists on monograde learners and ask each group to come up and write an element from their list on the flipchart paper. Continue with each group, each one adding something new to the list. Hang the paper on the wall so that everyone can see. Continue in this manner with the multigrade groups until you arrive at a similar list.

Review the two lists together and look for differences that exist only in multigrade. Ask participants to suggest what this means for multigrade classroom teachers. It is very important that teachers understand that the majority of the competencies necessary for good monograde teacher are also applicable to multigrade instruction.

Step 5

Action Research (30 mins)

Instructions:

Now that you have examined the different roles and competencies necessary to be effective in multigrade instruction, look at another tool that will help to move forward towards this objective: an action research journal.

The facilitator underlines the role of teachers as researchers. The teacher resolves the majority of challenges that occur in the classroom.

The facilitator presents the journal, particularly:

The place of the journal in learning/ action-research cycle

Possible advantages for individual practice

Contributions of lessons learned to the teachers' guide

Sharing with other teachers best lessons learned

The facilitator distributes journals to participants

As the next session will go focus on planning tools, ask participants to write in the journal, describing how they make their lesson plans for their classes. This may include responses to questions, such as:

What tools do you use?

Can these tools be used in multigrade planning?

How can you modify them so that they can be used on multigrade classrooms?

Step 6

Inventory/ Self-Evaluation (15 mins)

Instructions:

Distribute a self-evaluation worksheet to each participant.

Everyone should identify their level of understanding for each category and mark it on the form.

Underneath the category titles, everyone should identify one or two specific approaches that they want to improve in their multigrade classroom.

For each specific approach, mark their level of understanding

I want to learn more

I want to improve myself

I can do it

I can teach it

After the activity, it is important to collect all the worksheets and analyze them in order to identify the group's needs. What are their needs and what are competences that they already have? Who can help others? This information can help you in planning the rest of the training.

Session 2

Classroom Management Techniques and Strategies for Teaching and Learning

Objectives:

At the end of this session, participants should be able to:

Recognize techniques to ensure good classroom organization, classroom management and effective teaching strategies for multigrade

Identify challenges, resources and make suggestions for good classroom organization, classroom management and effective teaching strategies for multigrade

Materials:

Flipchart paper and markers

Daily objectives written on a piece of flipchart paper

An example of a lesson on flipchart paper

Journals

Questions for reflection on important techniques on a flipchart paper

Duration: 4 hours

Training Steps

Step 1

Reminder and Objectives of the Day (10 mins)

Instructions:

Thank the participants for coming back. Do a brief reminder of what they did during the previous day by underlining the multigrade activities. Then, present the day's objectives.

Step 2

Multigrade Lesson Simulations (90 mins)

Instructions:

Explain to participants that a member from each group will present a lesson created. Indicate that they will teach the lesson by pretending that the other teachers are learners.

Participants should work in their groups for 10-15 minutes and identifying a person who will present as well as how to present the lesson.

Invite all the groups to present. At the end of each presentation, ask:
What have you noticed about classroom organizations, classroom management and teaching strategies?

Are there other more efficient techniques?

What did the teacher do well and how might he or she can improve the lesson?

While participants respond to the above questions, the trainer puts up three different flipchart papers titled "Classroom Organization," "Classroom Management" and "Teaching Strategies." When participants respond, the trainer writes their responses on the corresponding flipchart paper.

Step 3

Priority Multigrade Technique (30 mins)

Instructions:

Once all the groups have presented, give each participant 2 stickers. Invite them to come up and place them on the flipcharts indicating the principal themes that they would like to discuss during the day.

If certain themes are missing, draw connections to them with those that have been chosen the most. Talk about time management, group work, pair tutoring, and teacher movements.

Given the stickers, the trainer must select 8 principal themes (with those mentioned above).

Step 4

Reflection on Priority Multigrade Techniques (60 mins)

Instructions:

Write up on the flipchart questions to consider during the reflection.

Ask participants to take out their journals.

Here are some questions to guide them:

What is the technique that you are exploring? How might you explain it to someone else?

What are the principal characteristics of this technique?

How it is used or how should it be used in a multigrade classroom?

What are the challenges of putting this technique into practice?

What are the strategies or suggestions for successfully putting this technique into practice?

After everyone has finished writing in their journals, they should separate into pairs to discuss their responses to the questions. They should agree on the main points to present and write up their observations about the questions on flipchart paper.

Step 5

Reporting Out Responses (45 mins)

Instructions:

Each group presents their flipchart paper. After each theme, participants should have time to make observations, comments, ask questions and add other points. Add to the flipchart and make clarifications as you go along.

Session 3 Monitoring and Evaluation

Objectives:

At the end of this session, participants should be able to:

Define the term “evaluation”

Identify the three types of evaluation

Identify examples of formative evaluation, apply them during training and identify examples of applied formative evaluation in their multigrade classrooms

Create a checklist and a scale to be used in class

Identify the necessary parts of a portfolio that can be used as an evaluation tool in their multigrade classrooms

Identify weaknesses and suggest methods to best formulate tests, compositions and other assessments

Materials

Flipchart paper (one sheet with three types of evaluation)

Markers

Independent activity worksheets

Paper and tape

Duration: 5 hours

Training Steps

Step 1

Introduction (5 mins)

Instructions:

Indicate the objectives for this session on a piece of flipchart paper. Read the objectives and present the goal of learner evaluation and the different types of evaluation.

Step 2:

What is “Evaluation?” (10 mins)

Instructions:

Distribute a card to each participant telling them to respond to the following question:

“ What is learner evaluation?”
When everyone has finished writing, invite them to read their responses out loud. The trainer writes up ideas and themes on a flipchart. The trainer should not correct the responses but at the end of the reporting should do a summary.

After having summarized, collect the cards and tell the teachers that you are going to look at them again at the end of the day during the formative evaluation.

Step 3

When Do We Evaluate Learning? (10 mins)

Instructions:

Put up a flipchart with the following questions: “When do we evaluate learning?” Invite participants to provide responses. While participants respond, the trainer should ask “who,” “when,” “where” and “how” in order to identify the roles of the evaluation.

After their responses, put up a flipchart with the types of evaluation and their explanations:

The flipchart will contain the following information:

Diagnostic evaluation	To do before teaching and/ or learning so that the teacher knows learner’s level and knowledge of the subject at the beginning
Formative evaluation	To do during teaching and/ or learning so that the teacher knows of their teaching help learners to achieve the objectives and goals of the lesson
Summative evaluation	To do at the end of the teaching and/ or learning to evaluate what learners have learned

Step 4

How Do We Do Formative and Summative Evaluations? (10 mins)

Instructions:

Ask participants, "How do we do formative and summative evaluations?" Put the responses on the flipchart.

Explain that the following section will highlight examples of tools that teachers can use within the classroom. It will address summative and formative evaluation.

Step 5

Introduction to Learning Corners Activity (10 mins)

Instructions:

You will need to prepare the classroom before beginning the session. This session is modeled on the multigrade technique of implementing learning corners. Thus, you will need to create four centers/ corners. Prepare signs so that everyone can use the subject area addresses. There should be four separate corners. The corners are as follows:

1st corner: Checklists and Scales

2nd corner: Portfolios

3rd corner: Written Assessment

4th corner: Formative Evaluation

Place all necessary materials in the corners, especially the independent learning activity worksheets (1st, 2nd and 4th corners).

Explain to participants that they will work within their group. Make a brief introduction for each of the corners. Explain the objective of each corner and indicate where each group will begin.

Be sure that participants understand that there are three corners with independent activity worksheets. In the 2nd corner, the trainer will provide a presentation on portfolios. Each group has 45 minutes for each corner. They need to produce a document for each corner (indicated by the worksheet located in each corner).

They should follow the instructions on the independent activity worksheets. Finally, indicate the direction that each group will take every 30 minutes.

Invite the groups to go to their corners.

Step 6

Learning Corners (3 hours)

Instructions:

While participants are working, circulate within the room. Assure that the group are working within the time allotted. There will be a timekeeper in each group but the trainer will also play this same role.

After 45 minutes, the groups should move to work in another corner. Before leaving, they should put up their flipchart sheet so that others can see their answers. When all groups have finished working, invite them to get up and view the flipchart papers posted around the room. Tell participants to circulate within the room to see other colleagues' work.

Step 7

Wrap-Up Activity (30 mins)

Instructions:

Take out the worksheets. Participants will write about:
A summary of what they did
Three things they learned related to the corners activity
1 question they have in relation to the subject matter and/ or activity
After 15 minutes, return to the large group and ask:

Impressions of the corner activity. Did they like the activity? Explain, How might they use it in their classrooms? How are they beneficial?
What do they think about the roles that they played during the corner work? How might they adapt it for their multigrade classes?

Step 8

Introduction to Micro-Teaching (5 mins)

Instructions:

Put up a flipchart that indicates the objectives for this session. Read the objectives and explain that they are going to practice the multigrade teaching strategies that they have learned throughout the training.

Step 9

Lesson Preparation (85 mins)

Instructions:

Write a lesson that involves a type of evaluation.

This lesson can address any subject. At the end of the preparation, someone will play the role of the teachers while the other participants will play the role of learners. They will have 15 minutes to perform the “micro-teaching.”

Step 10

Micro-Teaching Evaluation (135 mins)

Instructions:

Each group does a role play on a lesson for 15 minutes.

At the end of the lesson:

Group members make observations (strengths, difficulties, things to improve)

Trainers make observations

The second group performs their role play lesson and so forth.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this research ethical considerations were prioritized to ensure the protection and respect of all participants involved. Informed consent was obtained from the respondents, with a clear explanation of the study’s purpose, procedures, and potentials risks and benefits. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout the study by using codes instead of names and securely storing all data. Participation was entirely voluntary, with the option to withdraw at any time without penalty. No conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research. Moreover, the study adhered to institutional and educational ethical guidelines.

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